

DCH File Naming Guidelines

Version 1.0.0

1. Give unambiguous, meaningful, readable, but succinct names
2. Chose names that are safe across file and operating systems
3. Structure the filename and use filename extensions
4. Facilitate alphabetical sorting
5. Document your naming pattern

1 Give unambiguous, meaningful, readable, but succinct names

Select relevant characteristics of the file content as part of the names and use unambiguous labels for them. For example, use *en* and *it* (ISO 639-1) instead of English and Italian.

See: DCH File Naming Recommendations [doi:0.5281/zenodo.7447562](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447562)

2 Chose names that are safe across file and operating systems

Restrict the character inventory to the lowercase Latin alphabet *a-z*, digits *0-9*, hyphen (minus) *-*, and underscore *_*. Additionally, the full stop *.* is used once to separate the filename extension.

Example: `original-text_2009-04-23_001.mp4`

3 Structure the filename and use filename extensions

Separate parts of the name by underscore *_* and structure parts with hyphen (minus) *-*.

Example: `en_session-01_section-a.mp4`

4 Facilitate alphabetical sorting

Pad numbers with zeros to facilitate accurate sorting. Format dates following the YYYY-MM-DD (ISO 8601) pattern.

Example: `speaker-01_2009-04-23_take-001.wav`

5 Document your naming pattern

Document your naming pattern, ideally in the same location where the files can be found. For example, place a README file in the top folder of the project or dataset.

See: DCH Readme File Guidelines [doi:10.5281/zenodo.7447616](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7447616)